

CHARACTERISTIC OF POEMS WRITTEN FOR CHILDREN IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGE

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ANNOTATION

In this Article, the author tried to express his opinions about the history of the development of children's poetry written in the modern English and Uzbek language. In this, the author's focus is on children's poetry written in English and Uzbek as the main research material. In the process of preparing the article the author critically approached the views of English linguistic and boldly expressed his opinions. The article may be useful for those who study English and Uzbek translation studies and its lexicology.

Key words: translation, translation studies poetic translation romanticism poetry.

In the process of translating foreign language materials into the native language and native language materials into the foreign language, the ability to reflect grows, at one time intelligence, thinking, imagination, memory and speech, the ability to know is developed, since not a deep understanding of said thought but also skills to be able to perfectly and correctly express that thought in its native language are required the presence of extensibility in communication is of great importance in understanding and remembering new educational material. Therefore in the process of the joint activity of

the student with his teens, it is necessary to make a reservation that such an extirpation will appear in them.

It should be said that when giving readers poems written for children in foreign language, their content should be devoted to certain lexical or grammatical materials, for example by memorizing the poem “seasons”

The vocabulary of the reader may increase

Spring is green

Summer is bright

Autumn is yellow

Winter is white

The poem “Soap” can be given to further strengthen its quality.

Soap is green

Or red, or white

Or brown, or black

as ink!

But when you wash?

They all turn white

That is so strange

Think

This poem can be given to strengthen “present continuous”, “where are you going” Where are you going my little cat?

-I am going to town to get me a hat what! A hat for a cat! A cat in a hat who ever saw a cat in a hat?

Where are you going my little kittens?

-We are going to town to get us some mittens.

What! A wig for a pig!

Who ever saw a pig in a wig?

The poem of “Autumn” can be recommended for describe of Autumn

The summer is over,

The trees are all bare.

There is frost in the garden.

And frost in the air.

The poem “our day” can be recommended to express the routine of the day

Tea comes after dinner,

Then comes time to play

Now the day is over

And I go to bed. etc

It is clearly that there are specific difficulties in choosing a weight for poetic translation. When translating some works, previous experiences and usual weight are used, while translating others, it is necessary to look for new alternatives.

For instance, nowadays it is customary to turn syllabic-tonic works written in four. Stop iamb with the Uzbek $4+5=9$ and works written in five-stop iamb with $5+6=11$ or $6+7=13$, is entering.

But when translating some works, since the rhythm in them suddenly shifts to the second weight, it is necessary to find another functionally suitable form for this, the analysis of the translated work in terms of both content and form and the study of works written in Uzbek on this topic gave effective results. Let's try to clarify our opinion by searching for an alternative meaning for the translation of J.G. Byron's poem “ode” from French into Uzbek. If, the rhythm of verses changes from iambic to choreic, from choreic to iambic, and this change is inextricably linked with its content for example, the stage is beautifully decorated to spend the morning, aimed at understanding the sacredness of the feeling of the motherland. The national flag and coat of arms of Uzbekistan will be pictures of the beautiful nature of Uzbekistan, cultivated delicacies. The morning opens with an introduction by the speaker. Young people begin to form the word “Uzbekistan” with lively letters.

Uzbek found his identity on the day of sunbula the Z-time series is of irreversible purpose B-happiness will surely come to us if we are united

We strive for maturity, our human duty K-kamolot, my people strive for greatness. The dream of people is goodness, after all S-patience, faith is a companion T-may his life be peaceful, happiness will always be his companion oh, our dreams and intentions, may the whole world be at peace N-name is the mother country of Uzbekistan!!!

Guest 2

Well done, well done! May it always be safe. May your country and people always be prosperous.

Guest

What joy is this, what a celebration, why is everyone here ?

Reader

In our country there are many holidays, many weddings, generosity and hospitality are characteristic of my people singing the anthem of independent Uzbekistan is a light to our hearts and great to our hearts

But the structure of Uzbek poetry is very rich, it has the possibility to restore any rhythmic change, although not in the same way as in the original, but in other ways, but in a proportional function often, when comparing poems written in English and Uzbek on the same topic, functional adequacy is felt in their structure

To prove our point, let's turn to Uigun's work "Belbao girl" which describes the war horrors and memories. The heroine of the poem a girl who has just turned right years old-experiences the terrible pains of fascism. Her mother died under the roof of "Junkers" bombing later, the girl herself will die.

When the author describes the sad and scary scenes of the war, he does not express them in one rhythm. In only two stanzas of the poem, all verses are given in 4+5 weight the rhythm changes in the verses describing the worst horrors of the girl's life.

It is the most urgent issue to educate the youth, who are the owners of tomorrow, in the spirit of patriotism, national pride and pride. Because the future of the Motherland Cannot be imagined without young people. That is why the task of raising the future generation to become nature and well-rounded people is the most important

task of the president and the leadership of our country it is our honorable duty to educate the young generation in the spirit of loyalty to the rich cultural heritage of Uzbekistan, the symbols of our republic and to form a sense of pride in living in such a Motherland.

For this, it is necessary to skillfully use the factors that help to form a sense of patriotism at every moment to make people aware of their identity, to teach them to eat halal food and to raise them to be fighters for the happiness of the people.

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